

Original Article

Molybdenum and Methods of Application in Relation to Growth and Yield of Cabbage (*Brassica Oleacea* Var *Capitata* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Molybdenum benefits plants by acting as a crucial micronutrient that aids in enzyme activation, nitrogen fixation, improving synthesis of proteins and amino acids, promoting healthy growth, improving nutrient uptake, and enhancing crop yield. The goals of this investigation are to evaluate the effect of molybdenum and methods of application on the growth, yield, and yield attributes of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L.). This study was performed following a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with 3 replications and four distinct molybdenum dosages, viz., i) control ii) 1 kg/ha. iii) 2 kg/ha iv) 3 kg/ha and three methods of application, viz., i) 100% basal application, ii) 50% basal + 50% foliar spray, iii) 100% foliar spray were utilized in this investigation. 3 kg/ha molybdenum contributes to maximal plant height (37.73 cm), number of leaves (21.64), leaf length (38.56 cm), and breadth (32.03 cm). The highest plant height (36.53 cm), fresh weight of roots (50.65 g), head diameter (19.61 cm), and gross head weight (2.11 kg) were obtained from 100% foliar spray, but gross yield (78.54 t/ha), marketable head weight (1.08 kg), and marketable yield (54.19 t/ha) were found from the 100% basal application. The combined effect of molybdenum and methods of application has a significant influence on head diameter (21.93 cm), gross head weight (2.27 kg), gross yield (113.50 t/ha), marketable head weight (1.57 kg), and marketable yield (78.50 t/ha) for 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray. The plant growth, yield, and yield-attributing characteristics of cabbage were significantly influenced by the combination of 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray treatment.

Introduction

Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L.) is a highly nutritious and palatable leafy vegetable from the Brassicaceae

family widely cultivated in Bangladesh. In 2022, its total production in the country was approximately 395,035.65 metric tonnes from

21,500.63 hectares, with an average yield of 20.252 t/ha [1]. Originally discovered in the wilds of Europe, cabbage cultivation has expanded to countries such as China, Poland, Russia, Indonesia, the United States, and others. Globally, about 71.8 million tonnes of cabbages are produced annually, with China accounting for 47% of the total production [2].

Cabbage is cultivated for its densely leafed heads, typically grown during the first year of its biennial life cycle. It thrives in well-drained soil under full sunlight. Young cabbage plants develop a thin taproot with heart-shaped cotyledons, while mature plants reach 40–60 cm in height in their vegetative stage and 1.5–2 m during flowering [3]. The heads vary in size from 0.5 to 4 kg, depending on the variety, with early-maturing types producing smaller heads. Its leaves, usually thick and alternately arranged, range in shape from wavy to highly dissected, often displaying a waxy surface [4]. The plant's root system is fibrous and shallow, with most of the root mass concentrated within the upper 20–30 cm of soil, although lateral roots may extend up to 2 m deep [5].

Cabbage is a valuable source of protein, minerals, and vitamin A [6]. Its medicinal properties include aiding digestion, improving appetite, and benefiting diabetic patients. In addition, it is helpful in treat conditions like gastric ulcers, cholesterol issues, and skin cell damage. Ongoing research suggests that cabbage compounds such as sulforaphane and indole-3-carbinol may possess health benefits, including potential anticancer effects [7].

Fertilizers application is crucial for optimizing cabbage growth and yield. However, nutrient deficiencies, such as those of molybdenum (Mo), manganese (Mn), and magnesium (Mg), are widespread in Bangladesh due to insufficient fertilizer use [8]. Molybdenum plays a vital role as a catalyst in plant enzyme systems, improving yield, quality, and shelf life. Deficiency in molybdenum can lead to yellow-green chlorosis, inhibited head formation, and elongated leaves [9]. Although molybdenum levels in soil often exceed plant requirements, its absorption can be limited, making foliar application a more effective method for immediate nutrient uptake [10].

Farmers in Bangladesh increasingly cultivate cabbage due to its economic and nutritional

value. In light of its growing popularity, this study aims to identify the optimal molybdenum dose and application methods to enhance cabbage growth and yield while evaluating the combined effects of these factors. The findings could contribute to maximizing cabbage production and addressing nutritional deficiencies in the soil.

Materials and methods

Experimental site and design of the experiment

The experiment was conducted at the Horticulture Farm of Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU)S, Mymensingh, from November 2022 to February 2023, to evaluate the effects of molybdenum and its application methods on cabbage growth and yield. The experimental plot was a medium highland with silty loam soil, part of the Old Brahmaputra Floodplain (AEZ-9) as classified by UNDP (1988). The plot had remained fallow in the previous season. Soil samples from a depth of 0–20 cm was analyzed at the Humboldt Soil Testing Laboratory, Department of Soil Science, BAU. The experimental site, situated at 24°75' N latitude and 90°50' E longitude with an elevation of 18 m, experiences a subtropical climate. The rabi season (October to March) is characterized by moderate temperatures, minimal rainfall, and ample sunshine. Meteorological data on temperature, rainfall, humidity, and sunshine during the study were obtained from the Department of Irrigation and Water Management, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh.

The experiment involved two factors: molybdenum doses and application methods. Four molybdenum doses were tested: T₀ (control with no micronutrient), T₁ (1 kg/ha), T₂ (2 kg/ha), and T₃ (3 kg/ha). Moreover, three application methods were evaluated: M₁ (100% basal application), M₂ (50% basal + 50% foliar spray), and M₃ (100% foliar spray), resulting in 12 treatment combinations. The experiment was designed using a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications, in sum 36 plots. Each block contained 12 plots measuring 2 m × 2 m, with spacing of 50 cm between blocks and 40 cm between plots. The experimental layout was prepared using

measuring tools for precision. The cabbage variety used for this study was "Atlas 70," a

product of Asia Seed Co. Ltd., with seeds obtained from a dealer of Lal Teer Seed Limited.

Figure 1. The investigation area of Bangladesh

Land management and application of fertilizer

The experiment began with initial land preparation on November 10, 2022, by ploughing with a tractor and exposing the soil to sunlight. This was followed by cross-ploughing, leveling, and removing weeds and debris to achieve a fine tilth. Cinocarb 3G insecticide (4 kg/ha) was applied during the final preparation to protect plants from soil pests like cutworms and mole crickets. Molybdenum solutions were prepared using ammonium molybdate, diluted appropriately for application rates of 1, 2, and 3 kg Mo/ha. Fertilizers (N, P, K, S) were applied based on recommended rates, with portions incorporated during land preparation and later as topdressing. Twenty-day-old healthy cabbage seedlings were transplanted into the plots on November 29, 2022, with careful handling to avoid root damage. Intercultural operations included irrigation, gap filling, weeding, mulching, and earthing up. Irrigation was provided as needed, especially after topdressing and rainfall, ensuring no water transfer between plots. Weeding was done at 14, 29, and 44 days after transplanting to maintain weed-free plots, and mulching conserved soil moisture. Earthing up was performed at 20 and 40 days after

transplanting. To control pests and diseases, Malathion 57 EC (2 ml/L) and Ridomil MZ 68 (2 g/L) were applied, ensuring healthy growth and development.

Collecting data

Curd yield was measured on a plot basis, and five plants were randomly chosen from the middle rows of each plot for data collection in order to prevent boundary effects. Other characteristics were recorded during the vegetative stage, harvest, and post-harvest periods. Plant height and crown spread were measured at 30, 45, 60, and 75 days after transplanting (DAT).

Plant height was measured at 30, 45, 60, and 75 days after transplanting (DAT) from each plot using a meter scale, with measurements taken from the ground level to the tip of the largest leaf. The mean height of five selected plants from each plot was calculated and expressed in centimeters (cm). The number of leaves per plant was counted, excluding the smallest leaves from auxiliary shoots. Fallen leaves were counted based on the scar marks left on the stem by the petiole. The length of the leaves was measured from the base of the petiole to the tip

using a meter scale, and recorded in centimeters (cm). The breadth of the largest leaf was also measured with a meter scale and recorded in centimeters (cm). The length of the stem at harvest was recorded in centimeters, measured from the ground level to the unfolded leaves, and the average was noted. The number of days from sowing to visible head initiation was recorded by closely observing each plant from 35 DAT.

From 60 days after transplanting (DAT), each plant in the experimental plot was carefully monitored to determine the number of days required for maturation. The time taken from sowing to visible head initiation was recorded. The head diameter was measured at the point where the central head was cut off, with measurements taken in two dimensions using a

scale, and the average was calculated in centimeters (cm). The head thickness was measured vertically from the lowest to the uppermost leaves after sectioning the head, with the average thickness recorded in centimeters. The root length was recorded in centimeters at harvest as the distance from the ground level to the unfolded leaves, and the mean value was recorded. The fresh weight of the cabbage roots was determined by averaging ten plants in grams (g). The gross weight of ten sample cabbage heads, including loose leaves, was weighed, and the mean gross weight per plant was calculated in kilograms (kg) [11].

The cabbage from each unit plot was harvested and weighed for determination of gross yield per plot and was expressed in kilogram (kg), as well as measured by following formula [12].

$$\text{Gross Yield per Plot} = \frac{\text{Number of Plots}}{\text{Total Harvested Yield}}$$

The gross yield per plot were converted into yield per ha basis and expressed in ton/ha [13].

$$\text{Gross Yield} \left(\frac{\text{t}}{\text{ha}} \right) = \frac{\text{NPlot Area (m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Gross Yield per Plot (kg)}} \times 10,000$$

The loose leaves from all heads harvested from unit plot were removed and the heads were weighed for determining the marketable yield per plot and expressed in kilogram (kg). The

weight of marketable head per plot were converted to gain the yield per ha and recorded as ton/ha.

$$\text{Marketable Yield (t/ha)} = \frac{\text{Plot Area (m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Marketable Yield per Plot}} \times 10,000$$

Statistical analysis

The collected data for various characters were statistically analyzed using MSTAT computer package program. The means were calculated and the analysis of variance for each of the characters was performed by F (variance ratio) test. The differences between the treatment means were evaluated by LSD test at 1% or 5% probability wherever applicable.

Results

Effect of Molybdenum

The application of different molybdenum levels had a substantial impact on the plant's height. Plant height was observed to increase in conjunction with an increase in molybdenum. The T3 (3 kg/ha molybdenum) treatment resulted in the highest plant height (20.34, 31.17, 34.08, and 37.63 cm), while the T0 (control) treatment resulted in the lowest plant height (18.12, 25.01, 28.86, and 31.21 cm) at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Effect of molybdenum doses on plant height at different days after planting of cabbage

Figure 3. Effect of methods of application on plant height at different days after planting of cabbage

Major influences of molybdenum doses on the number of leaves were recorded on different days after planting, and it was noted that the influence of molybdenum doses on the production of foliage was considerable. The maximum number of leaves (13.42, 16.28,

19.47, and 21.64) were obtained at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP from 3 kg/ha molybdenum, and the smallest number of leaves (10.94, 13.67, 16.22, and 17.81) were produced at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP from the control treatment (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Effect of molybdenum doses on number of leaves per plant at different days after planting of cabbage

Figure 5. Effect of methods of application on number of leaves per plant at different days after planting of cabbage

The highest length of leaf of cabbage exhibited extremely substantial variation in response to distinct dosages of molybdenum treatment. The highest leaf length (38.56 cm) was attained at 75

DAP in 3 kg/ha molybdenum, while the lowest leaf length (21.19 cm) was obtained at 30 DAP from the control (Figure 5).

Figure 6. Effect of molybdenum doses on leaf length at different days after planting of cabbage

The width of cabbage leaves responded significantly to various dosages of molybdenum treatment. At 75 DAT, T3 (3 kg/ha

Figure 8. Effect of molybdenum doses on leaf breadth at different days after planting of cabbage

The application of molybdenum doses had significant effects on cabbage head formation, with 3 kg/ha molybdenum resulting in the shortest days (80.35 days) and the longest (96.55 days) compared to the control (Table 1). Applying molybdenum to cabbage had a substantial effect on its maturation period. The administration of 3 kg/ha molybdenum resulted in the minimum days to head maturity (102.33 days) and the longest days to head maturity (117.67 days) in the control treatment (Table 1). Applying molybdenum dosages significantly enhanced the diameter of cabbage heads. 3 kg/ha molybdenum resulted in the maximum head diameter with a value of 21.12 cm, whereas the

Figure 7. Effect of methods of application on leaf length at different days after planting of cabbage

molybdenum) had the largest leaf breadth of 32.03 cm, whereas the control treatment had the lowest (11.47 cm) at 30 DAP (Figure 8).

Figure 9. Effect of methods of application on leaf breadth at different days after planting of cabbage.

control treatment resulted in the smallest (17.42 cm) (Table 1). Different levels of molybdenum substantially affect the gross weight of cabbage heads. Maximum gross weight of head (2.17 kg) was obtained from 3 kg/ha molybdenum, and the minimal gross weight of head (1.46 kg) was obtained from the control treatment (Table 1). The weight of marketable head varied significantly among treatments due to diverse nutrition sources, and it appeared that the weight of marketable head was the greatest. The weight of marketable head (1.46 kg) was attained with 3 kg/ha molybdenum, whereas the control treatment yielded the lowest weight (0.90 kg) (Table 1). Several molybdenum dosages had

substantial effects on fresh root weight per plant. At 3 kg/ha, molybdenum produced the highest fresh root weight (59.09 g) and the lowest (41.08 g) from the control treatment (Table 1). The control treatment yielded the lowest marketable yield per plot (18.00 kg), while the optimum marketable yield per plot (29.20 kg) was derived from 3 kg/ha molybdenum (Table 1). A significant influence was observed among the

different doses of molybdenum on gross yield (t/ha). Gross yield per hectare of cabbage was substantially influenced by the various doses of molybdenum treatment. Maximum gross yield (108.28 t/ha) was obtained from 3 kg/ha molybdenum; the minimal gross yield (73.11 t/ha) was obtained from the control treatment (Table 1).

Table 1. Main effect of molybdenum doses and methods of application on growth and yield-attributing traits of cabbage

Molybdenum doses	Days to head formation	Days to head maturity	Fresh weight of roots (g)	Diameter of head (cm)	Gross weight of head (kg)	Gross yield (t/ha)	Weight of marketable head (kg)	Marketable yield/plot (kg)
T0	96.55	117.67	41.08	17.42	1.46	73.11	0.9	18
T1	89.11	114	45.67	18.8	1.7	84.78	1.26	25.17
T2	85.22	112	53.28	19.63	1.93	96.61	1.3	26.03
T3	80.35	102.33	59.09	21.12	2.17	108.28	1.46	29.2
LSD0.05	0.63	0.76	0.51	0.16	0.09	1.76	0.06	1.14
LSD0.01	0.86	1.04	0.69	0.22	0.13	2.6	0.08	1.55
LS	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
Methods of application								
M1	89.33	112.75	48.79	18.89	1.57	31.42	1.08	21.68
M2	88	111.5	49.9	19.22	1.76	35.25	1.21	24.25
M3	86.09	110.25	50.65	19.61	2.11	42.17	1.39	27.88
LSD 0.05	0.55	0.66	0.44	0.14	0.08	1.64	0.05	0.99
LSD 0.01	0.74	0.9	0.6	0.19	0.11	2.23	0.07	1.34
LS	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Here, LS= Level of significance, ** = Significant at 1% level of probability

Effect of methods of application

The primary effect of various application methods was a substantial variation in the height of the plants on various days following the planting. The highest plant (19.75, 29.38, 33.50, and 36.53 cm) was produced at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP using M3 (100% foliar spray), while the lowest plant (18.35, 27.54, 31.52, and 34.72 cm) was produced at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP using M0 (100% basal application) (Figure 3). The effect of various methods of application on the number of leaves per plant was highly significant for different days after planting. The largest number of leaves (12.40, 15.40, 18.10, and 20.42) were obtained at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP from M3 (100% foliar spray), and the least number of leaves (11.59, 14.31, 17.34, and

19.53) were obtained at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP from M0 (100% basal treatment) (Figure 5). The length of the largest cabbage leaf was significantly influenced by the method of application employed. The highest leaf length (36.17 cm) was observed at 75 DAP from 100% foliar spray, whereas the shortest leaf length (22.10 cm, 27.60 cm) was reached at 30 and 45 DAP from 100% basal treatment (Figure 6). The influence of methods of treatment on cabbage leaf breadth substantially differed. At 75 DAT, the maximum leaf breadth (29.31 cm) was attained with 100% foliar spray. The application method had a substantial impact on the number of days needed for cabbage head development. 100% foliar spray treatment required the fewest days (86.09), whereas 100% basal application required the most (89.33) (Figure 9). However,

application methods substantially influenced cabbage head maturation days. Minimum days required to attain maturity when 100% foliar spray was used, it required more days to reach head maturity compared to 100% basal treatment. Nevertheless, application techniques had a considerable impact on the diameter of cabbage heads. 100% foliar spray led to the greatest head diameter (19.61 cm), whereas 100% basal application led to the smallest head diameter (18.89 cm) (Table 1). On the other hand, methods of application also showed notable effects on the gross weight of the cabbage head. Maximum gross weight (kg) of head (2.11) was obtained from 100% foliar spray, while it was the minimal with a value of 1.57 kg (Table 1). In terms of application methods, it made a significant difference in the weight of a marketable head of cabbage. The maximum weight of marketable head (1.39 kg) was produced with 100% foliar spray, while the minimum weight (1.08 kg) was obtained with 100% basal treatment (Table 1). Distinct application methods had a significant impact on fresh root weight per plant. 100% foliar spray resulted in the highest fresh weight (50.65 g),

while 100% basal application ensued in the lowest (48.79 g) (Table 1). It is evident that gross yield (t/ha) recorded with the methods of application. The marketable yield per plot was determined to be highly significant as a result of the application methods. The maximum marketable yield per plot (27.88 kg) was achieved in 100% foliar treatment (Table 1). Maximum gross yield (105.42 t/ha) was obtained from 100% foliar spray; the minimal gross yield (78.54 t/ha) was obtained from the 100% basal application (Table 1).

Interaction effect of Molybdenum and methods of application

Significant variation in plant height was also observed as a result of the combined effects of molybdenum and various application methods. The highest plant height was achieved at 30 days after planting (21.01, 32.50, 34.50, and 38.75 cm). The lowest plant (17.79, 23.67, 27.33, and 30.00 cm) was obtained at 30, 45, 60, and 75 from the TOM0 (control and 100% basal application) at 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray (Table 2).

Table 2. Combined effect of molybdenum doses and methods of application on plant height and numbers of leaves of cabbage

Treatment combination	Plant height (cm)				Number of leaves			
	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP	75 DAP	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP	75 DAP
TOM1	17.79	23.67	27.33	30	10.38	13	15.75	17.63
TOM2	18	24.88	28	30.25	10.83	13.75	16.17	17.67
TOM3	18.56	26.5	31.25	33.38	11.63	14.25	16.75	18.13
T1M1	18.31	28.5	33	36.75	11.5	14.5	17.63	20.5
T1M2	18.42	29.25	33.13	37	11.88	15	18.25	20.75
T1M3	20.25	29.5	34.25	37.5	12	15.75	18.38	21
T2M1	17.67	28	32	35.25	11.5	14	17	19.25
T2M2	18.06	28.63	32.75	34.63	11.88	14.13	17.13	19.25
T2M3	19.17	29	34	36.5	12.21	14.5	17.38	19.88
T3M1	19.63	30	33.75	36.88	13	15.75	19	20.75
T3M2	20.38	31	34	37.25	13.5	16	19.5	21.5
T3M3	21.01	32.5	34.5	38.75	13.75	17.1	19.92	22.67
LSD 0.05	0.49	0.42	0.59	0.43	0.25	0.29	0.28	0.32
LSD 0.01	0.66	0.57	0.8	0.59	0.33	0.39	0.38	0.44
LS	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Here, LS= Level of significance, ** = Significant at 1% level of probability

Application of molybdenum levels and methods of application showed significant statistically

combined effects on the number of leaves. The maximum number of leaves (13.75, 17.10,

19.92, and 22.67) was produced at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP by the treatment combination of T3M3 (3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar application). The minimum number of leaves

(10.38, 13.00, 15.75, and 17.63) were observed at 30, 45, 60, and 75 DAP from TOM0 (control and 100% basal application) (Table 2).

Table 3. Combined effect of molybdenum doses and methods of application on leaf length and breadth cabbage

Treatment combination	Leaf length (cm)				Leaf breadth (cm)			
	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP	75 DAP	30 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP	75 DAP
T0M1	20.17	24.92	28	30.38	11.21	15.83	18.58	21.58
T0M2	21.54	26.63	28.5	30.42	11.24	17.5	21	23.5
T0M3	21.88	26.88	29.88	32.13	11.95	19.25	21.92	24.38
T1M1	21.5	28.5	31.5	35.25	12.53	20.75	25.25	29.25
T1M2	23.25	28.88	32	35.63	13.56	22.63	28.25	31
T1M3	23.56	29.88	34.58	36.75	14	24.5	29.04	32.29
T2M1	21.75	27.25	30.75	33.5	11.59	18.25	22.5	25
T2M2	22.5	27.75	31.88	34.5	12.38	20	22.88	25.13
T2M3	22.71	28.75	32.67	35.63	12.97	21.79	24	27.25
T3M1	25	29.75	31.5	37.5	15	24.5	28	31
T3M2	25.75	30	33.25	38	15.5	24.75	29	31.75
T3M3	27.17	32.33	34.75	40.17	16.5	26	30.17	33.33
LSD 0.05	0.43	0.38	0.64	0.47	0.25	0.36	0.41	0.69
LSD 0.01	0.59	0.51	0.87	0.64	0.34	0.49	0.56	0.94
LS	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Here, LS= Level of significance, ** = Significant at 1% level of probability

Table 4. Combined effect of molybdenum doses and methods of application on head formation days, head maturity days, head diameter, gross weight of head, marketable head weight, and fresh weight of roots of cabbage

Treatment combination	Days to head formation	Days to head maturity	Diameter of head (cm)	Fresh weight of roots (g)	Gross weight of head (kg)	Weight of marketable head (kg)	Marketable yield/plot (kg)
T0M1	98	118	17	40.65	1.14	0.8	16
T0M2	97	118	17.5	41.1	1.32	0.9	18
T0M3	94.67	117	17.75	41.5	1.93	1	20
T1M1	90.33	115	18.62	44	1.38	1.1	21.9
T1M2	89	114	18.77	46	1.62	1.16	23.2
T1M3	88	113	19	47	2.09	1.52	30.4
T2M1	86.67	113	19.51	52	1.76	1.13	22.6
T2M2	85	112	19.62	53.5	1.89	1.29	25.8
T2M3	84	111	19.76	54.33	2.15	1.49	29.7
T3M1	82.33	105	20.43	58.5	2	1.31	26.2
T3M2	81	102	21	59	2.23	1.5	30
T3M3	77.72	100	21.93	59.76	2.27	1.57	31.4
LSD 0.05	1.09	1.32	0.28	0.88	0.16	0.1	1.97
LSD 0.01	1.49	1.8	0.37	1.2	0.22	0.13	2.68
LS	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Here, LS= Level of significance, ** = Significant at 1% level of probability

The application of molybdenum levels and techniques of application both resulted in statistically significant combined impacts on leaf length. 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray produced the largest leaf length (40.17cm) at 75 DAP, while control and 100% basal application produced the shortest leaf lengths (20.17 and 24.92 cm) at 30 and 45 DAP (Table 3). The combination of 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray resulted in the highest leaf breadth (33.33 cm) at 75 DAP (Table 3).

The interaction effect of molybdenum doses and application methods was significant on cabbage head formation days. 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray resulted in the shortest days (77.72 days), while control and 100% basal application resulted in the longest days (98.00 days) (Table 4). Molybdenum levels and methods of application have a substantial impact on cabbage head maturity. The minimum days to head maturity (100.00 days) were achieved with 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray, while the maximum days required were 118.00 days with control and 100% basal treatment (Table 4). Molybdenum levels and application methods have a substantial influence on cabbage head diameter. The maximum diameter head (21.93 cm) was attained with 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar application. Control and 100% basal applications resulted in the lowest head diameter (17.00 cm) (Table 4). The gross weight of cabbage heads among the treatment combinations of molybdenum concentrations and methods of application was

considered statistically significant. The maximal gross weight of head (2.27 kg) was obtained from 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray; the minimum gross weight of head (1.14 kg) was obtained from control and 100% basal application (Table 4). The weight of marketable head among molybdenum dosage combinations and application methods was demonstrated to be statistically significant. The largest weight of marketable head (1.57 kg) was achieved from 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray, the minimal weight of marketable head (0.80 kg) was obtained with control and 100% basal treatment (Table 4). The minimum marketable yield per plot (16.00 kg) was achieved from control and 100% basal application, while the maximum marketable yield per plot (31.40 kg) was achieved from 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray (Table 4). Molybdenum dosages and application methods significantly impact the fresh weight of cabbage roots per plant. The highest fresh weight of roots per plant (59.76 g) was recorded with 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar spray, while the lowest fresh weight (40.65 g) occurred with control and 100% basal treatment (Table 4). Different levels of molybdenum and methods of application in combination had a significant influence on the total yield (t/ha). The maximum gross yield (113.50 t/ha) was attained from 3 kg/ha molybdenum and 100% foliar application. The minimum gross yield (57.17 t/ha) was obtained from control and 100% basal application (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Combined effect of molybdenum doses and methods of application on gross yield (t/ha) at different days after planting of cabbage

Discussion

Fertilizer enhances soil with macronutrients and micronutrients, supporting plant development. Fertilization is vital for the cultivation of excellent quality, high-yielding crops. Insufficient fertilization may retard growth, resulting in tiny and undeveloped heads. Cabbage is a high-yielding crop that can absorb more nutrients from soil. Proper fertilizer application is essential for ensuring enough nutrition distribution throughout the crop. Distinct doses of molybdenum and methods of application substantially influenced the growth and yield of cabbage. According to Yildirim et al. [14], foliar application gave better results than basal treatment. The study observed that higher levels of molybdenum and foliar application were associated with an increase in plant height and growth, as well as yield attributes. Rana et al. [9, 22] observed similar findings that the maximum plant height (36.41 cm), leaf length (27.32 cm), leaf breadth (23.50 cm), and diameter of head (15.31 cm) were achieved by utilizing foliar spray of 0.5% molybdenum on cabbage. Singh et al. [4, 23] observed the maximal plant height of cabbage (37.67 cm) with the foliar application of Boron B-20 @ 0.075% + Molybdenum @ 0.45%. Bhagawati et al. [15, 24] observed that boron and molybdenum promote the production of meristematic tissues, leading to increased vegetative growth, and additionally it was concluded that the soil treatment of borax and molybdenum was more effective than foliar spray, and cauliflower produced the maximum number of leaves per plant (18.3). Saha et al. [16, 21] found that in broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *italica* Plenck), the foliar application of ammonium molybdate at 0.05% at 45 DAT had a significant impact and resulted in a maximum central head diameter (8.26 cm), while using molybdate at 0.05% at 30+45 DAT alone or in combination improved plant height (51.43 cm), number of leaves per plant (13.68), and leaf length (28.97 cm). Prasad and Yadav [17] also suggested that the growth and yield of cauliflower plants were influenced by the foliar application of boron and molybdenum. Micronutrients influence the average weight of head, yield per plot, and yield per hectare of cabbage, and it was exhibited that Zn 1000 ppm

+ B 200 ppm + Mo 50 ppm is superior for growth parameters, i.e., plant height at 20, 35 DAT, and at harvest, number of leaves, average weight of head, yield per plot, and yield per hectare [18]. Ahmed et al. [19, 20, 25] demonstrated that molybdenum treatment had a positive and significant effect on the number of leaves per plant and marketable and non-marketable yields.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that molybdenum and application techniques substantially influence the growth, yield, and yield-attributing traits of cabbage. The application of 3 kg/ha molybdenum resulted in optimal plant height, number of leaves, leaf length, leaf width, days to head formation, and days to head maturity. The 100% foliar application exhibited better results in terms of day-to-head maturity, fresh root weight (g), head diameter (cm), and total head weight (kg). The experiment revealed that combining 3 kg/ha of molybdenum with 100% foliar spray resulted in the highest gross and marketable yield of cabbage.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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References

- Humayun Kabir, M. S. A., Das, B., Tanvir, M. S., Tanim, K. M. Y., Rahman, K. B., Islam, T., & Nuruzzaman, M. (2024). Effect of biochar on growth and yield of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata L.) in coastal region. *Journal of Bioscience and Agriculture Research*, 33(1), 2684-2696. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Uuh-Narvaez, J. J., & Segura-Campos, M. R. (2021). Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata): A food with functional properties aimed at type 2 diabetes prevention and management. *Journal of Food Science*, 86(11), 4775-4798. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Zahid, Z. H., Hoshain, S., Abuyusuf, M. D., Rahman, J. R., Rubel, M. H., & Ahmed, R. (2024). Morphophysiological and biochemical characterization of the exotic cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata L.). [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Singh, M. K., Singh, A. K., Singh, B. K., Pal, A. K., Singh, B., & Singh, R. K. S. P. (2021). Effect of foliar application of various micronutrients on growth characters of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata L.). *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 9(1), 1810-1813. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Patra, S. K., Poddar, R., Panda, R., Sarkar, A., Gaber, A., & Hossain, A. (2024). Response of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata L.) to different frequencies of irrigation and levels of soil fertilization in a non-saline coastal Typic Endoaquept. *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, 28(1), 6. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Singh, T. M., & Sharma, A. (2021). Constraints faced during the production and marketing of cabbage and potato crops: A comparative study of Manipur and Nagaland states of India. *Plant Archives*, 21(2). [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Coolong, T., Cassity-Duffey, K., & da Silva, A. L. B. R. (2022). Influence of nitrogen rate, fertilizer type, and application method on cabbage yield and nutrient concentrations. *HortTechnology*, 32(2), 134-139. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Laboni, S. H., Chowdhury, A. K. M. M. B., Bahadur, M. M., Islam, M. R., Hasan, M. M., & Howlader, N. C. (2024). Effect of different fertilizer combinations and gibberellic acid (GA3) on yield-attributing traits of mustard. *Journal of the Bangladesh Agricultural University*, 22(2), 185-192. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Rana, S., Barholia, A. K., Lekhi, R., Pippal, R., & Rana, P. (2019). Vegetative growth of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata L.) cv. Pusa Drum Head in relation to plant spacing, boron, and molybdenum. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 8(2S), 933-936. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Tehulie, N. S., & Belete, S. (2021). Review on the effects of NPS fertilizer rates on growth, yield components and yield of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata L.). *South Asia: Journal of South Asian Studies*, 1(1), 15-21. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Mia, S., Chandra, N., Tanvir, M., Bulbul, A., & Hasan, R. (2025). Comparative impacts of organic and inorganic fertilizers on the emergence and early growth of BARI Tomato-7 (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.). *Plant Physiology and Soil Chemistry*, 5(1), 1-3. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Howlader, N. C., Hossain, M. M., Rabbani, M. G., Basunia, A. K., Hasan, M. M., & Saima, U. (2023). Effect of irrigation intervals on the growth, yield, and fruit quality of lemon (*Citrus limon* L.). *Plant Physiology and Soil Chemistry*, 4(1), 20-24. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Yesmin, M. S., Sikder, M. S. I., Hossain, M. S., Hasan, M. M., & Howlader, N. C. (2023). Effect of organic seed priming on yield and yield-attributing traits of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) in drought-prone areas, *Agriculture Extension in Developing Countries*, 1(1), 38-42. [[Crossref](#)], [[Google Scholar](#)], [[Publisher](#)]
- Yildirim, E., Guvenc, I., Turan, M., & Karatas, A. (2007). Effect of foliar urea

application on quality, growth, mineral uptake and yield of broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* L., var. *italica*). *Plant Soil and Environment*, 53(3), 120. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

15. Bhagawati, R., VK, C., Devi, P., & Ronya, T. (2010). Effect of boron and molybdenum on growth, yield and quality of cauliflower in mid-altitude condition of Arunachal Pradesh. *Vegetable Science*, 37(2), 190-193. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

16. Saha, P., Chatterjee, R., Das, N. R., & Mukhopadhyay, D. (2010). Response of sprouting broccoli to foliar application of boron and molybdenum under Terai region of West Bengal. *Indian Journal of Horticulture*, 67 (Special Issue), 214-217. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

17. Prasad, V. M., & Dashrath Yadav, D. Y. (2003). Effect of foliar application of boron and molybdenum on the growth and yield of cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*) cv. Snowball-16. *New Agriculturist*, 14(1/2), 121-122. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

18. Patel, R. C., Patel, G. S., Acharya, S. K., Vadodaria, J. R., & Mori, C. V. (2021). Effect of micronutrients on growth and yield of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*). *International Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 17(1), 83-88. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

19. Ahmed, M. E., Elzaawely, A. A., & El-Sawy, M. B. (2011). Effect of the foliar spraying with molybdenum and magnesium on vegetative growth and curd yields in cauliflower (*Brassica oleraceae* var. *botrytis* L.). *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 7(2), 149-156. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

20. Hasan, M. M., Hossain, M. M., Haque, T., Basunia, A. K., & Howlader, N. C. (2025). Morpho-biochemical Evaluation of Three Sugar Apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) Genotypes. *International Journal of Horticultural Science and Technology*, 12(2),

189-198. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

21. Ali, M. S., Masum, M. A. A., Nazmul, S., Das, K. R., Howlader, N. C., & Hasan, M. M. (2025). Investigation of *Coccinia Grandis* Leaf Extract and Its Efficacy Against Stored Grain Pests. *SVU-International Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 7(1), 71-82. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

22. Hasan, M., Ahmed, K. S., Chandra Howlader, N., Hasan, M. M., Puja, M. S., Farhana, M. S., & Nikson, M. H. (2025). Optimization of Angoumois Grain Moth (*Sitotroga cerealella* Olivier) Infestation in Stored Grains as Influenced by Some Botanical Powders. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture - Food Science and Technology*, 13(2), 321-326. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

23. Rahman, M. T., Hasan, M. A., Hasan, M. M., Howlader, N. C., & Tusar, M. R. S. (2024). Impact of supplemental irrigation and organic manure on growth and yield performance of rice variety BRRI dhan103 under terminal drought condition in Aman season. *Bulg J Crop Sci*, 61(5), 21-31. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

24. Niksona, M. H., Ahmeda, K. S., Howladerb, N. C., Hasanb, M. M., Hasanc, M. R., Tanvir, M., ... & Ahmedc, M. Ecofriendly Management of Maize Weevil (*Sitophilus Zeamais*) As Influenced By Different Spices Powder. (2024). *Malysian Journal of Halal Research*, 7(2), 74-78. [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

25. Karim, F., Hossain, S. M. M., Hasan, M. M., Howlader, N. C., & Bhuiyan, M. M. A. (2024). Biological control of foot and root rot disease of pea by using formulated product of *Trichoderma*. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences (Belgrade)*, 69(2). [Crossref], [Google Scholar], [Publisher]

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